

PRINCIPLES OF UZBEK LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: *This article describes the methodology of teaching the mother tongue and the principles of teaching the mother tongue.*

Key words: *principle, orthographic literacy, speech, language, expressiveness of speech.*

Based on the task of teaching the native language to students, educating them and comprehensively developing them, knowledge is theoretically based, and based on the recommendations of all closely related disciplines, the methodology of teaching the native language develops its principles. These principles are different from general didactic principles and determine the directions of educational work between the teacher and the student. The principles of mother tongue teaching are as follows:

1. The principle of paying attention to language material, the growth of speech organs, and the correct development of speech skills. Ignoring the laws of speech and language, even if it is a little, has a negative effect on the acquisition of practical speech activities. For example, if phonetic skills are not given enough attention, spelling literacy will suffer. This educational principle requires the provision of auditory and visual instruction and training of the organs of speech (speaking, expressive reading, internal speech) in language classes.

2. The principle of understanding language meanings (lexical, grammatical, morphemic, syntactic meanings). Understanding a word, a morpheme, a phrase, a sentence means determining the connection between certain events in existence. The condition for following the principle of understanding the meanings of the language is to study all aspects of the language, all language-related subjects (grammar, lexicon, phonetics, orthography, methodology) in an interconnected manner. For example, morphology can be learned and mastered only by relying on syntax. In the study of syntax, one relies on morphology, orthography relies on phonetics, grammar, word formation, etc. Morphemic analysis of a word helps to understand its meaning. All aspects of the language are interconnected, and this must be taken into account in teaching.

3. The principle of developing language sensitivity. Language is a very complex phenomenon, without understanding its structure and coherent system, and without mastering its laws and similarities, it is impossible to keep it in mind. By talking, reading, listening, the child gathers language materials and learns its laws. As a result, a person develops language sensitivity (understanding of language phenomena).

4. The principle of evaluating expressiveness of speech. This principle is to understand the function of literate writing without understanding language phenomena, the communication function of the means of speech culture, understanding its expressiveness (related to style), not only its content, but also the emotional coloring of words and speech units, and other artistic and visual means of language. implies understanding. To follow this principle, first of all, it is necessary to use fiction, as well as other texts that clearly express the stylistic features of the language. This helps to understand the content of the text and its specific subtleties.

5. The principle of mastering oral speech before written speech. This principle also affects the development of human speech and serves in the formulation of language teaching methodology.

In conclusion, we can say that the principles of methodology, like the principles of didactics, help to determine the purposeful activity of the teacher and the student, to choose a convenient direction in their joint work, and serve as one of the elements of theoretical justification of methodology as a science.

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